

Multiple identity theorem

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abstract)

If an equation is a multiple identity, all terms of this equation must be have same exponent sum.

And this property will be used to prove the FLT, which is the step that

$$(X, Y, Z) = \left(\frac{G^n - R^n + L^n}{2}, \frac{G^n + R^n - L^n}{2}, \frac{G^n + R^n + Z^n}{2} \right)$$

Definition 1. exponent sum

It means all variable's exponent sum of a term.

For example, if a term

$$3R^8L^{13}$$

the exponent of R is 8.

And the exponent of L is 13.

The exponent sum of this term is

$$8 + 13 = 21$$

It is the exponent sum.

Definition2. multiple identity

If there exist a natural number solution (X, Y, Z) to some equation,

for any real number k , (kX, kY, kZ) is also a solution to the equation,

we will call this equation 'multiple identity'.

Lemma1.

By Definiton2, the Fermat equation is multiple identity.

$$X^n + Y^n = Z^n$$

if this equation has any natural number solution (x, y, z) , (kx, ky, kz) is also a solution of this equation. (k is a real number, and not zero)

$$(kx)^n + (ky)^n = (kz)^n$$

$$k^n x^n + k^n y^n = k^n z^n$$

Divide both sides by k^n .

$$x^n + y^n = z^n$$

This ordered pair (x, y, z) is a natural number solution of this equation by sumption.

What we ultimately prove for:

If an equation is a multiple identity for exponent sum n , all terms in this equation has same exponent sum, which is n . (n is any natural number bigger than 2)

First step. Theorem 1.

In multiple identity for exponent sum n , there cannot exist a term that exponent sum is $(n - 1)$.

For example,

$$3R^{n-2}L^2 + 8R^{n-3}L^3 - 34R^{n-5}L^5 + 2L^n = 0 \quad (\varphi 1)$$

This is a multiple identity. Because all terms have the same exponent sum, n . (n is a prime number bigger than 5)

However,

$$3R^{n-2}L^2 + 8R^{n-3}L^3 - 34R^{n-5}L^5 + 2L^n + 4L^{n-2} = 0$$

Can this equation can be multiple identity?

By the definition of multiple identity, this equation has a natural number solution $(R, L) = (r, l)$

$$3r^{n-2}l^2 + 8r^{n-3}l^3 - 34r^{n-5}l^5 + 2l^n + 4l^{n-2} = 0 \quad (\varphi 2)$$

Let this equation $(\varphi 2)$.

Look at the terms of ($\varphi 1$).

All terms of this equation have same exponent sum, n .

So if we substitute $(R, L) = (\sqrt[n]{2}R, \sqrt[n]{2}L)$,

all terms become twice.

$$3R^{n-2}L^2 \rightarrow 3 \times 2^{\frac{n-2}{n}} R^{n-2} \times 2^{\frac{2}{n}} L^2 = 3 \times 2 \times R^{n-2}L^2$$

$$8R^{n-3}L^3 \rightarrow 8 \times 2^{\frac{n-3}{n}} R^{n-3} \times 2^{\frac{3}{n}} L^3 = 8 \times 2 \times R^{n-3}L^3$$

⋮

etc.

All terms that their *exponent sum* = n become twice, when we substitute $(\sqrt[n]{2}R, \sqrt[n]{2}L)$

But in ($\varphi 2$), there exist a term that don't be twice, when we substitute $(r, l) = (\sqrt[n]{2}r, \sqrt[n]{2}l)$

$$4l^{n-2} \rightarrow 4 \times 2^{\frac{n-2}{n}} l^{n-2}$$

Let's think about it. If a multiple identity has a natural number solution (r, l) , we can make another natural number solution by multiplying by k (kr, kl) .

In $(\varphi 2)$, all terms except $4l^{n-2}$ become twice by substitute

$$(r, l) = (\sqrt[n]{2}r, \sqrt[n]{2}l)$$

Therefore all terms except $4l^{n-2}$ is an integer.

But! $4l^{n-2} \rightarrow 4 \times 2^{\frac{n-2}{n}} l^{n-2}$ is not an integer. Because n is a prime number and $2^{\frac{n-2}{n}}$ is always an irrational number.

So we can obviously know that if we assume that $(\varphi 2)$ is a multiple identity, this equation cannot have any natural number solution (r, l) .

Because by the property of multiple identity, $(\varphi 2)$ must have another natural number solution. But it is impossible.

Therefore we can get the conclusion that, if an equation is multiple identity (like FLT), and if we assume that there is a natural number ordered pair (X, Y, Z) , each variable in this ordered pair must have the same exponent sum.

In general, when substituting $(r, l) = (\sqrt[n]{2}r, \sqrt[n]{2}l)$,

terms with exponent sum $(n - 2)$ produce a $2^{\frac{n-2}{n}}$ component.

Also, terms with exponent sum $(n - 1)$ produce a $2^{\frac{n-1}{n}}$ component.

Terms with exponent sum $(n - 3)$ produce a $2^{\frac{n-3}{n}}$ component.

⋮

Terms with exponent sum 3 produce a $2^{\frac{3}{n}}$ component.
(for example, $RL^2 \rightarrow 2^{\frac{3}{n}}rl^2$)

Terms with exponent sum 2 produce a $2^{\frac{2}{n}}$ component.

Terms with exponent sum 1 produce a $2^{\frac{1}{n}}$ component.
(for example, $R \rightarrow 2^{\frac{1}{n}}r$)

And, since n is a prime number,

$$2^{\frac{1}{n}}, 2^{\frac{2}{n}}, 2^{\frac{3}{n}}, \dots, 2^{\frac{n-3}{n}}, 2^{\frac{n-2}{n}}, 2^{\frac{n-1}{n}}$$

are cannot canceled each other by multiplying any integer.

$$2^{\frac{1}{n}} \times Z_1 + 2^{\frac{2}{n}} \times Z_2 + \dots + 2^{\frac{n-2}{n}} \times Z_{n-2} + 2^{\frac{n-1}{n}} \times Z_{n-1} \\ \neq (\text{integer})$$

(where Z_i is an integer)

Only the terms with exponent sum n (or multiple of n) can produce an integer coefficient and find next multiple solution.

And we also note that

exponent sum $\equiv 1 \pmod{n}$ \rightarrow produces $2^{\frac{1}{n}}$ component.

exponent sum $\equiv 2 \pmod{n}$ \rightarrow produces $2^{\frac{2}{n}}$ component.

exponent sum $\equiv 3 \pmod{n}$ \rightarrow produces $2^{\frac{3}{n}}$ component.

\vdots

exponent sum $\equiv (n - 2) \pmod{n}$ \rightarrow produces $2^{\frac{n-2}{n}}$ component.

exponent sum $\equiv (n - 1) \pmod{n}$ \rightarrow produces $2^{\frac{n-1}{n}}$ component.

Therefore, if an equation is a multiple identity, there must not be any term with exponent sum where the remainder when divided by n is

$$1, 2, 3, \dots, (n - 2), (n - 1).$$

Only the terms with exponent sum n or multiples of n can exist in the multiple identity.

Then can the terms with exponent sum n and $2n$ can be coexist in the multiple identity?

No. Why?

For example,

$$2R^n + 5R^{n-2}L^2 - 8R^{n-5}L^5 + 3RL^{n-1} \\ = (\text{exponent sum } n \text{ for variables } R, L)$$

$$3R^{2n-1}L + R^{2n-6}L^6 - 9R^{2n-7}L^7 + 2L^{2n} \\ = (\text{exponent sum } 2n \text{ for variables } R, L)$$

Since a multiple identity has any natural number solution (r, l) ,

(kr, kl) must be also a natural number solution.

In the equation, the terms with exponent sum n : move left-hand side.

The terms with exponent sum $2n$: move right-hand side.

Then, assume that (r, l) is a natural number solution of this equation. Therefore, the following equation holds.

$$2r^n + 5r^{n-2}l^2 - 8r^{n-5}l^5 + 3rl^{n-1} \\ = -3r^{2n-1}l - r^{2n-6}l^6 + 9r^{2n-7} - 2l^{2n} \quad (\varphi 3)$$

Then, we know that if (r, l) is a solution of this equation,

$(2r, 2l)$ is also a solution of this equation.

But when we substitute $(2r, 2l)$, the left-hand side increases by 2^n . But the right-hand side increases by 2^{2n} .

It looks impossible. Yes. It's a contradiction. Because it negates equation (3).

Also exponent sum n with $3n, 4n, 5n, \dots$ etc. cannot coexist.

We also can substitute $(3r, 3l)$

let the terms with exponent sum $n = (n\text{th equation})$

Then $(n\text{th equation}) \rightarrow 3^n \times (n\text{th equation})$

$(2n\text{th equation}) \rightarrow 3^{2n} \times (2n\text{th equation})$

$(3n\text{th equation}) \rightarrow 3^{3n} \times (3n\text{th equation})$

⋮

etc.

Then when we divide all terms by 3^n , all terms except $(n\text{th equation})$ are multiples of 3^n .

Therefore $(n\text{th equation})$ must be a multiple of 3^n .

And this process can be repeated by substituting

$$(r, l) = (5r, 5l)$$

Then (n th equation) must be a multiple of 5^n .

If we substitute $(r, l) = (7r, 7l)$,
then (n th equation) must be a multiple of 7^n .

Same way,

(n th equation) is a multiple of $3^n \times 5^n \times 7^n \times 11^n \times \dots$

Therefore (n th equation) = infinite.

It is contradiction. Since (r, l) is integers, (n th equation) must be finite natural numbers. It is impossible.

Integer solution was not exist.

We already know in FLT, ordered pair (X, Y, Z) must satisfy the form

$$(X, Y, Z) = \frac{1}{2}(G^n - R^n + L^n, G^n + R^n - L^n, G^n + R^n + L^n)$$

The Fermat equation is a multiple identity. Therefore $(2X, 2Y, 2Z)$ is also a natural number ordered pair.

$$(2X, 2Y, 2Z) = (G^n - R^n + L^n, G^n + R^n - L^n, G^n + R^n + L^n)$$

Then X, Y, Z are all composed of variables whose exponent sum is n .

And we know that

$$G \mid Z \rightarrow G \mid (G^n + R^n + L^n)$$

But remember Z is not a multiple of G^2 .

Therefore

$$G \mid (R^n + L^n)$$

And G, R, L are coprime each other, so we can express G by using two variables, R, L .

$$G = aR + bL$$

$$(a, b \in \mathbb{Z})$$

If
 $(R^n + L^n)$ is a multiple of $G = (aR + bL)$,

There must be factoring method $f(R, L)$, where

$$R^n + L^n = (aR + bL) \times f(R, L)$$

Then, by multiple identity theorem, and since FLT is multiple identity,

all terms of $f(R, L)$ must be have same exponent sum, $(n - 1)$.

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} f(R, L) &= a_1 R^{n-1} + a_2 R^{n-2} L^1 + a_3 R^{n-3} L^2 + \dots + a_{n-3} R^3 L^{n-3} \\ &+ a_{n-2} R^2 L^{n-2} + a_{n-1} R^1 L^{n-1} + a_n L^n \end{aligned}$$

Then we can check the only way that $(aR + bL) \times f(R, L)$ become $R^n + L^n$ is

$$a = 1, b = 1$$

Therefore $G = R + L$ is the only way to satisfy FLT, which is multiple identity.

Thank you for reading.

References

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